

No differential effect on body composition or inflammation in the presence or deprivation of gluten in the diet of nonceliac fitness practitioners. Corollary remarks on their approach to health management.

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Both authors are independent researchers. AF is the current legal representative of *To fit* sports association, officially registered with the Italian National Olympic Committee (CONI). He coordinated communication and relationships with participants, prescribed personalized physical activity programs, performed bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA) measurements and collected all the data. GL is a licensed physician registered with the Italian Medical Council, and retired from previous institutional affiliations. He conceived the project, carried out the medical check-ups and wrote the manuscript.

Abstract

Awareness of the importance of an appropriate alimentary regimen as a determinant of health status has been paralleled by the spread of do-it-yourself measures often based on incorrect information, among which the increased consumption of gluten-free foods has emerged even in the absence of medical motivation or intolerance.

This observational study compared the effect of a 3-month diet with or without gluten, combined with regular and structured physical activity, on body mass index (BMI), body composition, and inflammatory markers in 53 amateur nonceliac fitness practitioners.

We observed an overall improvement in body composition, expressed by significant reduction in BMI and increase in phase angle, musculoskeletal mass and body cell mass as measured by bioelectrical impedance analysis, regardless of the presence or absence of gluten in the diet. No evidence has emerged for a role of gluten in inflammation: platelet count, that nevertheless remained within normal limits, significantly decreased in both groups, while other inflammatory indexes were unchanged. The results do not support the hypothesis that gluten elimination may confer additional benefits in terms of body composition or inflammation compared with a balanced diet with gluten in nonceliac subjects. Finally, the sensitivity and dedication shown by participants, especially females, towards non-medical determinants of health seemed not matched by comparable attention for preventive medicine and early diagnosis.

Introduction

The concept of health has evolved from absence of disease to an idea of complete well-being, which is not just the product of a sanitary organization, but depends on a series of environmental and behavioral factors.

At the same time, individuals became increasingly aware of their role and responsibility in lifestyle choices comprising non-medical determinants of health [1], such as diet, physical activity, respect for biorhythms, and consumption of tobacco and psychotropic substances, including alcohol.

In Italy, about 35 percent of the population engages in regular physical activity and about 9.5 percent of the adult population is a member of a fitness gym [2].

According to a recent report [3], as many as 51 percent of the population follows a diet, of which only around a third under nutritionist's prescription and supervision.

Data have been reported of a pro-inflammatory effect of gluten [4] with potential role in the manifestation and course of illnesses other than celiac disease [5].

A growing increase in the consumption of gluten-free foods even in the absence of medical rationale or intolerance has been reported [6], due to self-limitations based on personal beliefs, information not properly applied to one's case, or even not fully validated [7].

We thus found it useful to verify in a group of fitness-practicing nonceliac volunteers the effects of a 3-month diet, balanced and of individualized caloric intake, differing in the presence or absence of gluten, on indices of body composition as measured by bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA) and on some parameters expressing inflammation and metabolism.

As a corollary of the study, the participants were offered medical evaluation with history and physical examination to assess their overall health status and the relationship between its strictly medical aspect and other determinants.

Population and methods

Participants were recruited on a voluntary basis among the members of a gym in the city of Padua by posting for three weeks on the bulletin board an invitation to participate in

the study, while enjoying a free diet personalized in relation to individual needs and body mass index (BMI).

For the same period, flyers with the same content were left in the gym spaces and changing rooms. The sample population can be taken as a reference for the average person with specific awareness towards well-being features related to nutrition and physical activity. The aim was to collect a sample of at least 50 participants and recruitment was concluded after 62 adhesions, in anticipation of a dropout rate of around 15%, in line with the average value reported in the literature for observational studies [8].

Participants were assigned to the gluten or non-gluten group based on the individual preferences expressed by the individuals, or, in the absence thereof, randomly.

We are aware that such assignment may represent a bias, that anyway would not have been eliminated by full randomization, due to possible conflict between personal convictions and the assigned diet.

The diet was set by the same registered dietitian according to BMI and age following the principles of the Mediterranean diet [9] with a composition of 50% carbohydrates, of which no more than $\frac{1}{4}$ as monosaccharides and disaccharides; 25% fats, $\frac{2}{3}$ of which unsaturated; and 25% proteins, preferably of vegetal origin, therefore with a slight increase in the protein quota as compared to the 15-20% indicated in the guidelines [10], considering the usefulness of protein supplementation in those who perform physical activity [11]. Appropriate hydration was prescribed to all participants.

Each participant continued to regularly train according to the individual schedule already in use, as prescribed by the same professional trainer with a master degree in movement science.

Prior to the start and at the end of the diet, body composition was measured by means of bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA) with Akern BIA 101 scale (Pisa, Italy) and Akern electrodes.

BIA is based on the different ability of water and tissues to conduct or resist an electric current and, based on algorithms that consider sex, age and anthropometric values of the subject, allows to quickly and non-invasively evaluate the state and variations of body composition [12], both in conditions of well-being [13] and in multiple states of illness [14].

The parameters used in this study were phase angle, extracellular water, skeletal muscle mass, and body cell mass.

The Phase Angle (PHA) expresses the ratio between the resistance opposed by cells and fluids. It is expressed in degrees; its value is higher in males in relation to greater muscle mass and for the same reason it tends to decrease with age [15]. A reduction in its value may indicate damage to cell membranes and/or expansion of extracellular volume, as in the case of edema and water retention. A low phase angle is associated with states of malnutrition, inflammation and prolonged physical inactivity [16] and represents a significant risk for the development of a state of frailty [17].

Extracellular Water (ECW) represents the set of liquids outside the cells and its value is expressed in liters.

Skeletal muscle mass (SMM) expresses the amount of striated muscle responsible for motor activity and its value is measured in kilograms (kg).

Body cell mass (BCM), also measured in kilograms, is the non-fat body mass minus the bone mineral component and extracellular water and represents the compartment with the greatest metabolic activity [18]. It is an expression of overall health [19], strength, and resilience[20].

The measurements were performed by the same operator and the subjects were fasting, had not consumed alcohol or caffeine nor had exercised in the previous 8 hours and had emptied their bladder before the measurement. Most of the measurements were taken between 8 and 10 a.m. In few subjects this was not possible in relation to work requirements. In all cases, the measurements were performed at the same time in the same subject.

By means of venous blood sampling complete blood count, protein electrophoresis, fibrinogen, C-reactive protein (CRP) and blood glucose were determined before the start of the diet and after its end . The analyses were carried out in laboratories accredited according to international standards and certified in compliance with applicable regulations. The requests for blood tests were made by the respective general practitioners. All participants provided informed written consent to participate and publish data. The study involved no interventions and was conducted in accordance with ethical principles for observational research.

Statistical significance was assessed by two-tailed t-tests for paired or unpaired data unless otherwise stated, using Microsoft Excel for Mac (version 16.98). Linear regression analyses were also performed using Microsoft Excel. Multivariate analysis of variance, expressed as Pillai's trace, was conducted in R (version

4.3.1) within RStudio (version 2025.05.1+513), using the base ``manova()`` function on the delta values of 19 parameters measured before and after the observation period, namely BMI, PHA, ECW, SMM, BCM, SMM/BMI ratio, BCM/BMI ratio, total white blood cell count, neutrophil count, lymphocyte count, platelet count, mean red blood cell volume, hematocrit, hemoglobin, blood glucose, fibrinogen, α_1 globulin, α_2 globulin and CRP.

Differences in categorical variables between independent groups were assessed by Pearson's Chi-squared test using 2×2 contingency tables, also computed in R. Changes in paired categorical variables were evaluated by McNemar's test without continuity correction, performed in R using the built-in ``mcnemar.test()`` function with ``correct = FALSE``.

A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant for all tests.

Finally, participants were offered, by means of an individual private communication sent by e-mail, a free visit, including history, physical examination and evaluation of the baseline laboratory parameters investigated, by an internist with a strong clinical background.

All those who underwent such visit were given a written report, the content of which was discussed with the interested party, with the relevant data and recommendation to any further diagnostic and/or therapeutic investigations to the attention of the respective family physicians as far as they were concerned. No intervention or prescription was therefore made and the medical action was strictly limited to evaluation and reporting.

Results

Of the 62 people who joined the project, 9 (M = 7; F = 2), or 14.5%, dropped out. 53 subjects (M = 14; F = 39) completed the study and data for them alone were considered. The mean age was 42.6 ± 10.3 years, with no difference between sexes (M = 43.3 ± 9.8 ; F = 42.3 ± 10.6 , n.s.). The mean body mass index (BMI) was 23.6 ± 3.4 . BMI was higher in males than in females (25.7 ± 2.6 vs. 23.0 ± 3.4 , $p < 0.01$), and no correlation between age and BMI was observed nor in the whole group nor in either subgroup by sex. In no subject was the BMI less than 18.5. In 13 subjects (24.5%) BMI was ≥ 25 . Of these, 8 were males (57.1%) and 5 females (12.8%, $\chi^2 = 8.67$, $p = 0.003$).

At baseline, bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA) values showed mean phase angle (PHA) values of 6.48 ± 0.7 degrees; extracellular water (ECW) 16.96 ± 2.6 liters; skeletal muscle mass (SMM) 26.21 ± 5.9 kg and body cell mass (BCM) 29.81 ± 6.3 kg. A linear inverse correlation between age and PHA was observed at baseline ($r = -0.352$; $F = 6.0$; $p < 0.05$). No significant correlation was observed between age, expressed as an independent variable, and any of the other BIA parameters explored (ECW, SMM, BCM). A significant linear correlation between BMI and skeletal muscle mass (SMM) was observed at baseline conditions ($r = 0.386$; $F = 8.9$; $p < 0.005$) and between BMI and body cell mass (BCM) ($r = 0.481$; $F = 15.4$; $p < 0.0005$). As shown in Figures 1 and 2, a close linear correlation between PHA and SMM and between PHA and BCM was observed.

Figure 1. Linear correlation between phase angle (PHA) and skeletal muscle mass (SMM) at baseline in study subjects ($r = 0.543$; $F = 21.3$; $p < 0.00005$).

Figure 2. Linear correlation between phase angle (PHA) and body cellular mass (BCM) at baseline in study subjects ($r = 0.680$; $F = 44.1$; $p < 0.000001$).

Basal laboratory tests documented 10 cases (M = 2; F = 8) of mild to moderate macrocytosis ($96.1-103 \mu^3$); 5 cases of mild normochromic anemia (Hb 11.2-12.2 g/dL) associated in 2 cases with mild neutropenia (1.23 and $1.7 \times 10^9/L$) and in 1 case with mild lymphopenia ($1 \times 10^9/L$); 2 cases of microcythemia consistent with thalassemia trait; 1 case of borderline thrombocytopenia ($140 \times 10^9/L$); 2 cases of minimal elevation in blood glucose (111 and 112 mg/dL) and CRP (0.56 and 1.40 mg/dL); and the presence of a monoclonal component of uncertain significance in the gamma region in 2 cases with no other meaningful alterations in the electrophoretic pattern in the remaining cases. All the other parameters explored were within normal limits. A significant linear correlation between age and blood glucose was observed at baseline conditions ($r = 0.371$; $F = 8.1$; $p < 0.001$). No other significant correlation was observed between age and any of the other parameters explored in blood.

28 people (53%; M = 5; F = 23) booked for medical examination and 2 of the 5 males did not show up for the appointment. Allergy to drugs, food or environmental substances was reported in 6 cases; tobacco consumption, autoimmune disease and gastroesophageal reflux in 3 cases; untreated arterial hypertension and hypercholesterolemia in 2 cases; osteopenia in 1 case. Heart murmur, hepatomegaly, patellar hyporeflexia and painful

colon were observed at physical examination in 3 cases each and odontopathy in 2 cases. The general conditions of all the people examined were on the whole good, the objective findings did not raise particular concerns and laboratory alterations were mild. However, only 4 of them had fully unremarkable physical examination and normal laboratory tests. Of the others, in 9 cases the alterations that emerged, though not severe but worthy of further investigation, were reported previously unknown by the interested parties and further 3 cases received recommendations according to commonly accepted guidelines to carry out prophylactic cancer screening which they had not attended.

Of the 53 persons (M = 14; F = 39) who completed the study, 26 subjects (M = 5; F = 21; average age 42.2 ± 10.3 ; mean BMI 23.8 ± 3.9) were assigned to the gluten-free diet (GFD) group and 27 subjects (M = 9; F = 18; average age 42.9 ± 10.5 ; mean BMI 23.5 ± 2.9) to the gluten-containing diet (GCD) group.

There were no significant differences in mean age, BMI or any of the baseline values of all the investigated parameters between the two groups. The difference in sex distribution, as assessed by Pearson's chi-squared test, was also not statistically significant.

As illustrated in Fig. 3, phase angle (PHA) significantly increased after diet, either in the whole group (WG) from 6.48 ± 0.7 to 6.72 ± 0.7 degrees, $p = 0.001$ and both in the GFD, from 6.62 ± 0.6 to 6.90 ± 0.7 , $p = 0.02$, and GCD, from 6.34 ± 0.8 to 6.54 ± 0.7 degrees, $p < 0.01$, subgroups.

Figure 3. Change in phase angle (PHA) after three months of diet in the total, gluten-free diet (GFD) and gluten-containing diet (GCD) groups studied. Data on the ordinate are expressed in degrees.

Changes in BMI, SMM and BCM after diet are shown in Fig. 4. BMI significantly decreased: WG from 23.63 ± 3.4 to 22.94 ± 3.3 , $p < 0.00001$; GFD from 23.77 ± 3.9 to 23.04 ± 3.6 , $p = 0.0001$; GCD from 23.50 ± 2.9 to 22.84 ± 3.0 , $p < 0.00001$. SMM significantly increased : WG from 26.21 ± 5.9 to 27.23 ± 6.0 kg, $p < 0.00001$; GFD from 25.72 ± 5.3 to 26.82 ± 5.7 kg, $p < 0.0005$; GCD from 26.68 ± 6.4 to 27.63 ± 6.4 kg, $p < 0.01$. BCM significantly increased as well : WG from 29.81 ± 6.3 to 30.89 ± 6.7 kg, $p < 0.00005$; GFD from 29.81 ± 6.1 to 30.98 ± 6.6 kg, $p < 0.005$; GCD: from 29.81 ± 6.7 to 30.80 ± 6.9 kg, $p < 0.005$.

Figure 4. Change in body mass index (BMI), skeletal muscle mass (SMM) and body cellular mass (BCM) after three months of diet in the total, gluten-free diet (GFD), and gluten-containing diet (GCD) groups studied. Data on the ordinate for SMM and BCM are expressed in kilograms.

Fig. 5 shows the significant increase in the ratio between SMM and BMI : WG from 1.11 ± 0.22 to 1.19 ± 0.23 , $p < 0.00001$; GFD from 1.09 ± 0.22 to 1.17 ± 0.23 kg, $p < 0.00001$; GCD from 1.14 ± 0.23 to 1.21 ± 0.23 kg, $p < 0.00005$; and between BCM and BMI: WG from 1.27 ± 0.22 to 1.35 ± 0.23 , $p < 0.00001$; GFD from 1.26 ± 0.22 to 1.35 ± 0.24 kg, $p < 0.00001$; GCD: from 1.27 ± 0.23 to 1.35 ± 0.23 kg, $p < 0.00001$.

Figure 5. Change in the ratio of skeletal muscle mass to body mass index (SMM/BMI) and body cellular mass to body mass index (BCM/BMI) after three months of diet in the total, gluten-free diet (GFD) and gluten-containing diet (GCD) groups studied.

ECW only minimally decreased from 16.96 ± 2.6 to 16.85 ± 2.5 liters, n.s.

Platelet count significantly decreased in all the groups: WG from 261 ± 53.9 to $241 \pm 54.9 \times 10^9/L$, $p < 0.00005$; GFD: 263 ± 61.9 to $244 \pm 61.0 \times 10^9/L$, $p = 0.002$; GCD from 258 ± 46.0 to $238 \pm 49.3 \times 10^9/L$, $p < 0.005$.

Mild macrocytosis increased from 10 to 16 cases (McNemar exact test, $p = 0.014$) without difference between subgroups (GFD from 5 to 7; GCD from 5 to 9, χ^2 n.s.).

White blood cell count, fibrinogen, α_1 globulin, α_2 globulin and CRP slightly decreased, but changes were not significant.

A significant blood glucose decrease was observed from 82.4 ± 9.5 to 78.6 ± 8.2 mg/dL, $p < 0.001$ in the whole group. While still present in both subgroups, such decrease was statistically significant only in the GFD subgroup, from 84.1 ± 7.2 to 79.5 ± 9.7 mg/dL, $p = 0.002$. In the GCD subgroup the decrease in blood glucose was from 80.8 ± 11.2 to 77.8 ± 6.6 mg/dL, $p = 0.085$, but there was no significant difference between the two subgroups.

No statistically significant differences were found in pre-post changes between the GFD and GCD groups for any of the investigated parameters.

This finding was confirmed by multivariate analysis of variance, which assessed differences between the GFD and GCD groups. The test yielded non-significant results, as indicated by Pillai's trace = 0.319; $F(19,33) = 0.81$; $p = 0.677$.

In a nutshell, therefore, we observed after dieting significant reduction in BMI, platelet count and blood glucose; significant increase in PHA, SMM, BCM, SMM/BMI and BCM/BMI ratios and in the prevalence of mild macrocytosis. And no significant difference between the GFD and GCD subgroups.

Discussion

Awareness of the importance of a salubrious lifestyle as a determinant of health status is increasing, also as a result of campaigns by governments and health authorities [21,22]. Internet and social networks can play a significant positive role in this regard [23], but at the same time may cause the spread of incorrect information [24], which can rise to the rank of truth among many for the sole fact of being present on the net and largely shared. The increased consumption of gluten-free foods even in the absence of medical motivation or intolerance [25] responds to reasons without scientific foundation [26], according to which they are healthier, have greater nutritional value or anti-inflammatory power.

The proponents of the inflammatory theory of gluten base their assumptions on in vitro observations, on epidemiological data involving a multiplicity of different factors in addition to gluten, or on reports about the negative role of gluten in some diseases, without, however, being licit to transpose such data, not even definitely confirmed, into the general population.

It is a fact, however, that a high percentage of high-level athletes, and up to the top level, declare that they take a gluten-free diet with benefit [27].

The first study on the effect of a gluten-free diet on some parameters and physical performance of athletes was published in 2015 [28] and to our best knowledge, no others on the specific topic were published.

It therefore seemed useful to compare the effect of a diet with or without gluten on some parameters of body composition, metabolism and inflammation in a group of apparently healthy fitness practitioners.

This population seemed suitable for the study due to the sensitivity and orientation towards a healthy lifestyle and the possibility of repeated contact, on the occasion of periodic training in the gym, for the support and verification of the correct progress of the project.

The average body mass index (BMI) of the participants was normal; 24.5% of them had BMI > 25, compared to the national figure of 47.6% of overweight or obese people [4] and, unlike what happens in the general population [29], no correlation was observed between age and BMI, confirming that they were keeping fit.

The small number of tobacco users (3/53 = 5.7%, compared to 24% of the national population) is also in line with the figure.

BMI is the most widely used index for assessing the state of nutrition, but it is not able to differentiate the constituents of body composition and their changes [30].

Bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA) is useful in this regard due to the speed, ease and repeatability of use in the absence of invasiveness.

According to previous literature [15], an inverse linear correlation between phase angle (PHA) and age has been observed.

No correlation between BMI and PHA has been observed, since PHA is an expression of qualitative parameters, which do not necessarily depend on the amount of body mass, but rather on its cellular characteristics.

A strong linear correlation was observed between BMI and both skeletal muscle mass (SMM) and body cell mass (BCM), consistent with the interpretation that, in physically active individuals, higher BMI values may reflect increase in lean and metabolically active tissues.

The even closer correlation observed between PHA and SMM and between PHA and BCM is just as assertive of the measurement of phase angle as an expression of muscle and cellular quality.

As far as blood tests are concerned, the numerically most represented abnormal data was mild-moderate macrocytosis (96.1-103 μ^3 , reference values: 80-96), which was found in 18.9% of subjects and can be explained on a deficiency basis [31] or by alcohol intake [32].

Though in contrast with other group's healthy habits, the second hypothesis appears more likely, also in the light of the subsequent findings of a further increase in cases of macrocytosis, considering that alcohol users often deny or do not recognize the problem themselves [33].

The linear correlation observed between age and blood glucose confirms what is known in this regard [34], in relation to reduced insulin secretion and decreased sensitivity to its action.

The association of three months of diet with structured and constant gym exercise resulted in a significant functional metabolic improvement in body composition, as expressed by a reduction in BMI with an increase in PHA, SMM and BCM, and a reduction in blood glucose.

The increase in the SMM/BMI and BCM/BMI ratio and the absence of changes in ECW confirm that the reduction in BMI was associated with a qualitative improvement in body composition due to an increase in its metabolically active component.

Improvement in body composition was observed in the sample considered as a whole and in both subgroups that have taken gluten or not, with no differences between them.

The significant reduction in platelet count as a possible expression of inflammation should be considered with extreme caution; while the role of platelets, besides their pro-coagulant function, is widely established also in immunological processes [35], their number cannot be associated with an inflammatory state when it falls within normal limits, and even less as isolated data in the individual.

Other inflammatory indices slightly, though not significantly, decreased.

The set of data, statistically confirmed also by multivariate analysis of variance, do not support the hypothesis that gluten elimination may confer additional benefits in terms of body composition or inflammation compared with a balanced diet with gluten in nonceliac subjects.

The lower reduction in blood sugar in the gluten-containing group diet (GCD) can be explained by stricter adherence to the diet program by the members of the gluten-free diet group (GFD), more motivated to give up food rich in carbohydrates due to the possibility of the associated presence of gluten, typically pasta or sweets, to which the members of the GCD group may have conceded some tears due to the lower fear of failing at the essential point of the program.

The explanation for the increase from 10 to 16 cases of macrocytosis remains uncertain.

An increase in alcohol intake can be interpreted as compensating for dietary restrictions, also in relation to the local culture of the region, which is fourth in the country for alcohol consumption.

Anyway, prevalence and incidence of macrocytosis were not different in groups with or without gluten, excluding a role in this regard as well.

Within the general concept of health of which physical activity and nutrition are part, it seemed useful to collect data on how these aspects are perceived and coordinated with the medical health aspects in the sample analyzed.

The speed of recruitment to the study, its low dropout rate and the results obtained confirm the sensitivity and dedication of the participants towards non-medical determinants of health, in particular by females, who represented three-quarters of the entire group.

The attention to prevention and early diagnosis seems to be lower in the sample studied. In fact, less than half of the participants ($26/53 = 49\%$; M = 3, F = 23) has benefited from medical examination.

9 of the 26 people visited showed evidence worthy of further investigation of which they were not aware and another 3 had not carried out prophylactic screenings indicated according to commonly accepted guidelines.

In 11 of the 27 people not examined, one of the laboratory alterations reported in the results was present. It is of course not possible to establish whether the indifference to the medical aspects of the study is due to lack of consideration in this regard, or to adequate follow-up in a different location, thus making the one offered redundant.

The set of data, however, seems to show in the sample studied more interest in the training and nutrition aspects of health than in the medical ones.

Ethical approval.

This was a non-interventional observational study involving healthy volunteers. All participants provided written informed consent for participation and publication; for the one minor participant, consent was obtained from the mother, who held legal parental authority. All data were anonymized. No ethical approval was required for this type of research, as the authors did not perform any intervention, but merely collected data either through non-invasive measurements obtained via a bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA) scale, or from laboratory test results prescribed by the participants' general practitioners and voluntarily provided to the researchers.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Data availability: All data underlying the results are available as part of the article and no additional source data are required. This project contains the following underlying data:

raw_data_full.xlsx

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Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

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References

- 1) Ministero della Salute. Stili di Vita. Last updated 30 July 2025. https://www.salute.gov.it/resources/static/pubblicazioni/Stili_di_vita.pdf
- 2) Truenumbers. Palestre di fitness gli Italiani iscritti sono 5,5 milioni. Last updated 30 July 2025. <https://www.truenumbers.it/palestre-italia/>
- 3) Unisalute. La metà degli italiani segue una dieta, ma pochi si affidano a uno specialista. Last updated 20 July 2025. https://www.unisalute.it/wcm/connect/85bb12a1-0630-4338-ba92-71262c4f42a1/Osservatorio+Sanità+UniSalute_Alimentazione.pdf?MOD=AJPERES&CVID=oZMHBHW#:~:text=La%20prima%20notizia%20è%20che,oggi%20sono%20ben%20il%2051%25
- 4) De Punder K and Pruinboom L. The dietary intake of wheat and other cereal grains and their role in inflammation. *Nutrients* 2013 Mar 12;5(3):771-87. DOI: [10.3390/nu5030771](https://doi.org/10.3390/nu5030771)
- 5) Philip A and White ND. Gluten, Inflammation, and Neurodegeneration, *Am J Lifestyle* 2022 Jan 11;16(1):32-35. DOI: [10.1177/15598276211049345](https://doi.org/10.1177/15598276211049345)

- 6) Eurispes. Risultati del Rapporto Italia 2023. Last updated 30 July 2025.. <https://eurispes.eu/news/risultati-del-rapporto-italia-2023/>
- 7) Zingone F, Bertin L., Maniero D et al. Myths and Facts about Food Intolerance: A Narrative Review. *Nutrients* 2023 Nov 30;15(23):4969. DOI: [10.3390/nu15234969](https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15234969)
- 8) Robinson KA, Dennison CR, Way DR et al. Systematic review identifies number of strategies important for retaining study participants. *J Clin Epidemiol* 2007 Aug; 60(8):757-65. DOI: [10.1016/j.jclinepi.2006.11.023](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2006.11.023)
- 9) Martínez-González MA, Gea A, Ruiz-Canela M. The Mediterranean Diet and Cardiovascular Health. *Circ Res* 2019 Mar; 124(5):779-798. DOI: [10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.118.313348](https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.118.313348)
- 10) European Commission. Dietary recommendations for protein intake for adults and older adults. Last updated 30 July 2025. https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/health-promotion-knowledge-gateway/dietary-protein-intake-adults-3_en
- 11) Morton RW, Murphy KT, McKellar SR et al. A systematic review, meta-analysis and meta-regression of the effect of protein supplementation on resistance training-induced gains in muscle mass and strength in healthy adults. *Br J Sports Med* 2018 Mar; 52(6):376-384. DOI: [10.1136/bjsports-2017-097608](https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2017-097608)
- 12) Lukaski HC, Johnson PE, Bolonchuk WW, Lykken GI. Assessment of fat-free mass using bioelectrical impedance measurements of the human body. *Am J Clin Nutr* 1985 Apr; 41(4):810-7. DOI: [10.1093/ajcn/41.4.810](https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/41.4.810)
- 13) Kyle UG, Bosaeus I, De Lorenzo AD et al. Bioelectrical impedance analysis--part I: review of principles and methods. *Clin Nutr* 2004 Oct; 23(5):1226-43. DOI: [10.1016/j.clnu.2004.06.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2004.06.004)
- 14) Kit-Chung Ng, Lik-Fung Lau, Chun-Kau Chan G et al. Nutritional Assessments by Bioimpedance Technique in Dialysis Patients. *Nutrients* 2023 Dec 20; 16(1):15. DOI: [10.3390/nu16010015](https://doi.org/10.3390/nu16010015)
- 15) Yamada Y, Buehring B, Krueger D et al. Electrical Properties Assessed by Bioelectrical Impedance Spectroscopy as Biomarkers of Age-related Loss of Skeletal Muscle Quantity and Quality. *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci* 2017 Sep 1; 72(9):1180-1186. DOI: [10.1093/gerona/glw225](https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/glw225)
- 16) Wirth R, Volkert D, Rösler A et al. Bioelectric impedance phase angle is associated with hospital mortality of geriatric patients. *Arch Gerontol Geriatr* 2010 Nov-Dec; 51(3):290-4. DOI: [10.1016/j.archger.2009.12.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archger.2009.12.002)
- 17) Tanaka S, Ando K, Kobayashi K et al. Low Bioelectrical Impedance Phase Angle Is a Significant Risk Factor for Frailty. *Biomed Res Int* 2019 Jun 10:2019:6283153. DOI: [10.1155/2019/6283153](https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/6283153)

- 18) Cimmino F, Petrella L, Cavaliere G et al. A Bioelectrical Impedance Analysis in Adult Subjects: The Relationship between Phase Angle and Body Cell Mass. *J Funct Morphol Kinesiol* 2023 Jul 28; 8(3):107. DOI: [10.3390/jfmk8030107](https://doi.org/10.3390/jfmk8030107)
- 19) Castizo-Olier J, Irurtia A, Jemni M et al. Bioelectrical impedance vector analysis (BIVA) in sport and exercise: Systematic review and future perspectives. *Plos One* 2018 Jun 7; 13(6):e0197957. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0197957](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0197957)
- 20) Branco Garcia M, Mateus C, Capelas ML et al. Bioelectrical Impedance Analysis (BIA) for the Assessment of Body Composition in Oncology: A Scoping Review. *Nutrients* 2023, 15(22), 4792. DOI: [10.3390/nu15224792](https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15224792)
- 21) Istituto Superiore di Sanità. Gain health. Last updated 30 July 2025. <https://www.epicentro.iss.it/guadagnare-salute/>
- 22) World Health Organization. European health report 2018: more than numbers – evidence for all. Last updated 30 July 2025. <https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/9789289053433>
- 23) Liu J. Promoting a healthy lifestyle: exploring the role of social media and fitness applications in the context of social media addiction risk. *Health Educ Res* 2024 May 11; 39(3):272-283. DOI: [10.1093/her/cyad047](https://doi.org/10.1093/her/cyad047)
- 24) Del Vicario M, Bessi A, Zollo F et al The spreading of misinformation online. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2016 Jan 19; 113(3):554-9. DOI: [10.1073/pnas.1517441113](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1517441113)
- 25) Zerbini C, De Canio F, Martinelli E, Luceri B. Are gluten-free products healthy for non-celiac consumers? How the perception of well-being moderates gluten-free addiction. *Food Quality and Preference*. Volume 118. September 2024, 105183.
- 26) Arslain K, Gustafson CR, Baishya P, Rose D. Determinants of gluten-free diet adoption among individuals without celiac disease or non-celiac gluten sensitivity. *Appetite* 2021 Jan 1; 156:104958. DOI: [10.1016/j.appet.2020.104958](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2020.104958)
- 27) Jansson-Klodell CS, Rubio-Tapia A. The fashionable gluten-free diet- wear with caution. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2021 Mar 11; 113(3): 491-492. DOI: [10.1093/ajcn/nqaa371](https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/nqaa371)
- 28) Lis D, Stellingwerff T, Kitic CM et al. No Effects of a Short-term Gluten-free Diet on Performance in Nonceliac Athletes. *J Sci Med Sports Exerc* 2015 Dec; 47 (12): 2563-2570. DOI: [10.1249/MSS.0000000000000699](https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000000699)
- 29) Villareal DT, Apovian C, Kushner RF, Klein S. Obesity in older adults: technical review and position statement of the American Society for Nutrition and NAASO, The Obesity Society. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2005 Nov; 82(5):923-34. DOI: [10.1093/ajcn/82.5.923](https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/82.5.923)
- 30) Biolo G, Di Girolamo FG, Breglia A et al. Inverse relationship between “a body shape index” (ABSI) and fat-free mass in women and men: Insights into mechanisms of sarcopenic obesity. *Clin Nutr* 2015; 34; 323-327. [10.1016/j.clnu.2014.03.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2014.03.015)

- 31) Allen RH, Stabler SP, Savage DG, Lindenbaum J. Metabolic abnormalities in cobalamin (vitamin B12) and folate deficiency. *Faseb J* 1993 Nov; 7(14):1344-53. DOI: [10.1096/fasebj.7.14.7901104](https://doi.org/10.1096/fasebj.7.14.7901104)
- 32) Thompson a, King K, Morris A, Pirmohamed M. Assessing the impact of alcohol consumption on the genetic contribution to mean corpuscular volume. *Hum Mol Genet* 2021 Oct 13; 30(21):2040-2051. DOI: [10.1093/hmg/ddab147](https://doi.org/10.1093/hmg/ddab147)
- 33) Schuckit MA, Clarke DF, Smith TL, Mendoza LA. Characteristics associated with denial of problem drinking among two generations of individuals with alcohol use disorders. *Drug Alcohol Depend*. 2020 Sep 10;217:108274. DOI: [10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2020.108274](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2020.108274)
- 34) Chaudhari R, Khanna J, Rohilla M et al. Investigation of Pancreatic-beta Cells Role in the Biological Process of Ageing. *Endocr Metab Immune Disord Drug Targets*. 2024; 24(3):348-362. DOI: [10.2174/1871530323666230822095932](https://doi.org/10.2174/1871530323666230822095932)
- 35) Ali RA, Wuescher LM, Worth RG. Platelets: essential components of the immune system. *Curr Trends Immunol*. 2015; 16:65–78.